

ADJUSTMENT AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

*Rohit Bhandari

ABSTRACT

This study examines the adjustment of senior secondary school students in relation to their emotional intelligence. The sample of the study consisted of 100 eleventh class students (50 boys and 50 girls) studying in government and private schools of Chandigarh. A descriptive survey method was employed to collect the data. The major findings of the study revealed a significant difference in adjustment of students studying in government and private schools in favour of students studying in government school. Further, the adjustment level of students with high emotional intelligence was significantly higher than the students with low emotional intelligence.

Key Words: Adjustment, Emotional Intelligence

****Assistant Professor***

Dev Samaj College of Education, sector 36/B , Chandigarh, India

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays life is very complex and ever evolving due to heightened competition. These complexities of life are affecting the lives of adolescents as well. They are becoming more restless, aggressive and developing negative attitudes towards things. This in turn results in their poor adjustment with the surroundings and persons. With the progress of time, one learns how to interact with one's own social surroundings. This aim can be fulfilled only by proper understanding of the individual and his abilities and aptitudes. Education is a social concept, philosophically evolved, psychologically developed and socially based. The main function of education is to make the person social. It is no more a mere communication of knowledge or the acquisition of few skills learnt mechanically

Adjustment refers to the psychological processes through which human beings manage and cope with the demands, challenges, and frustrations of everyday life. It is the achievement of a state of equilibrium between the individual and his physical-social environment. It is a lifelong process in which an individual learns ways of behavior through which he enters into a harmony with his environment. In the present study, the term adjustment covers different areas of human experiences and interactions. When a person adjusts well in areas i.e. emotional adjustment, social adjustment, educational adjustment and total adjustment, he is called a well-adjusted person. James Drever (1952) referred to adjustment as the modification to compensate for or meet special conditions. Carlo and Raffaelli (2002) studied the differential relations of parent and peer attachment to adolescent adjustment and discovered that the adolescents who were high on both parent and peer attachment were the best adjusted. Bhalla (2022) concluded that there existed a significant difference in personal adjustment of African and Asian university students.

Emotional intelligence is the ability of an individual to know, manage and control his own emotions and to know about other's emotions. Emotional intelligence helps an individual to adapt to his environment or to mould the situation as per his own requirements. Goleman (1999) stated that emotional intelligence is the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of others for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in ourselves and in our relationships. A study conducted by Barbey et al. (2023) found significant overlap between general intelligence and emotional intelligence, both in terms of behavior and in the brain. Findings of the study conducted by Jaeger (2002) revealed a strong relationship between emotional intelligence and academic performance.

OBJECTIVES

1. To compare the adjustment of government and private senior secondary school students.
2. To compare the emotional intelligence of government and private senior secondary school students.
3. To compare the adjustment of senior secondary school students with regard to gender.
4. To compare the emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students with regard to gender.

5. To study the adjustment of senior secondary school students in relation to their emotional intelligence.

HYPOTHESES

1. There will be no significant difference in adjustment of government and private Senior Secondary school students.
2. There will be no significant difference in emotional intelligence of government and private senior secondary school students.
3. There will be no significant difference in adjustment of senior secondary school students with regard to gender.
4. There will be no significant difference in emotional intelligence of senior secondary school students with regard to gender.
5. There will be no significant difference in adjustment of senior secondary school students in relation to their emotional intelligence.

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

In the present study, a descriptive survey method was employed to collect the data. Adjustment was a dependent variable and emotional intelligence was an independent variable.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

Stratified random sampling technique was employed in the present study. The sample comprised 100 students from two senior secondary schools students of Chandigarh. Out of these, 50 students were selected randomly from each government and private school. Further 25 male and 25 female students were taken from each type of school i.e. government and private.

TOOLS OF THE STUDY

1. Adjustment inventory for school children by Sinha and Singh
2. Mangal's Emotional Intelligence Inventory by Mangal and Mangal

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE

The obtained data was analyzed by employing t-test.

RESULTS

Table 1

Mean Differentials in Adjustment and Emotional Intelligence of senior secondary students studying in government and private schools

Variable	Mean		S.D		t-value	Level of Significance
	Govt. School	Pvt. School	Govt. School	Pvt. School		
Adjustment	21.05	14.58	4.36	6.84	5.81	0.01
Emotional Intelligence	53.94	52.21	7.81	8.32	0.352	Not Significant

Table 1 shows that mean differential with regard to Adjustment of senior secondary students studying in government and private schools is statistically significant at .01 level ($t = 5.81$). This indicates that the senior secondary students studying in government school ($M = 21.05$) are better in Adjustment as compared to senior secondary students studying in private school ($M = 14.58$). Hence, hypothesis 1 stands rejected. Further, no significant difference ($t = 0.352$) has been found in emotional intelligence of senior secondary students studying in government and private schools. It indicates that the both government and private senior secondary school students have almost equal level of emotional intelligence. Hence, hypothesis 2 stands accepted.

Table 2

Mean Differentials in Adjustment and Emotional Intelligence of senior secondary male and female students

Variable	Mean		S.D		t-value	Level of Significance
	Male	Female	Male	Female		
Adjustment	18.32	19.08	5.83	6.51	0.283	Not Significant
Emotional Intelligence	52.12	50.82	9.32	8.21	0.954	Not Significant

Entries made in table 2 shows no significant difference in both Adjustment ($t = 0.283$) and emotional intelligence ($t = 0.954$) of senior secondary male and female students as t-values were not found to be statistically significant. It indicates that Adjustment and emotional intelligence of senior secondary male and female students are almost same. Hence, hypotheses 3 and 4 stand accepted.

Table 3

Mean differences in Adjustment of senior secondary students with regard to Emotional Intelligence

Group	Mean	S.D	t-value	Level of Significance
High Emotional Intelligence	22.84	5.62	3.276	0.01
Low Emotional Intelligence	13.45	6.21		

From the results in Table 3, it is clear that t-value with regard to adjustment of senior secondary students with high and low emotional intelligence is statistically significant at .01 level ($t = 3.276$). This indicates that adjustment level of students with high emotional intelligence ($M = 22.84$) was better as compared to the students with low emotional intelligence ($M = 13.45$).

Hence, hypothesis 5 stands rejected.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

The study revealed that there is a significant difference in the level of adjustment of students with regard to their emotional intelligence. So it becomes necessary for a teacher to know the importance of emotional intelligence for effective education. Successful learning requires students to interact closely with teachers and peers which in turn make them well-adjusted. This study suggests that parents and teachers should broaden the mental horizon of the children so that they feel more recognized and accepted in their world and more and more co-curricular activities like debates, declamations should be organized to enhance the social skills of the students. The study also highlights emotional intelligence as a novel concept which is considered to be more decisive a factor in one's success than general intelligence. Emotional intelligence can be developed through all such activities where the students get an opportunity for understanding their own emotions and emotions of others and empathizing with them. These activities can be some act of social service or showing sensitivity towards the environment. Hence, it becomes vital for the teachers to know the concept of emotional intelligence and help the students develop it to succeed academically.

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